

“Combating Discrimination, Violence and Harmful Practices Against Intersex Persons”

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Introduction

Intersex individuals in Pakistan are generally not integrated within mainstream society, owing to cultural and socio-religious biases. They are pushed to the outskirts of social life as part of the Khawaja Sira community, a distinct subculture consisting of marginalised gender-nonconforming individuals who defy traditional notions of gender and sexuality (Nisar 2021). Their social exclusion is translated into legal marginalisation, as the legal system fails to protect them against widespread abuse and discrimination. This submission explores legal barriers intersex individuals face, analysing how Pakistan’s legal system has been unable to meet its obligations under treaties like the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) and the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) (OHCHR, n.d.).

1. Legal Background and Recognition of Intersex Individuals in Pakistan

1.1 The Khawaja Sira Community and Legislative Recognition

The *Khawaja Sira* community, which includes intersex people, has a significant historical legacy as a distinct ‘third gender’ category preceding the creation of Pakistan. This group gained formal

statutory recognition through the Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act of 2018, seven decades post-independence, giving individuals the prerogative to identify as male, female, or third gender on official documents (Nisar, 2021). The Act was intended to protect rights of gender-nonconforming people, but ambiguities in the legislation, especially in defining intersex individuals, causes significant issues.

Section 2(n)(i) subsumes intersex individuals in a broader category of ‘transgender’, defining ‘intersex’ as “Intersex (Khunsa) with a mixture of male and female genital features or congenital ambiguities.” Other subcategories of ‘transgender’, within the Act, are ‘khwaja sira’ and ‘transgender man or woman’. (Pakistan Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act, 2018). This categorisation is not reflective of wider societal understanding of the different forms of gender-nonconformity, which considers, as discussed above, ‘*Khawaja Sira*’ as the umbrella term for all gender-nonconforming people. Consequently, given the conservative socio-religious backdrop of Pakistan, this Act became a major controversy due to its supposed incompatibility with Islamic law (Kalbe Ali, Dawn News, 2022).

The Federal Shariat Court, in May 2023, ruled the sections 2(f), 3 and 7 of the Transgender Act 2018 which relate to gender identity being self-perceived, the right to official recognition of gender identity and the right of inheritance for transgender, or more accurately, gender non-conforming people. Following this, the option to select the “X” category on CNIC cards, given by the Supreme Court in the case of *Dr. Muhammad Khaki versus S.S.P Rawalpindi (PLD 2013 SC 188)*, was revoked and intersex individuals found

that they could no longer make that selection when renewing their documents.

This effectively rendered them stateless, reversing the progress that has already been made.

1.2 Constitutional and International Legal Obligations

Theoretically speaking, intersex individuals have always been entitled to legal protection from discrimination. Article 25 of Pakistan's Constitution provides for equality before the law, mirroring Article 25 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR). However, Article 26(1), which prohibits discrimination on the basis of sex, actually allows the same in case of public places used for religious purposes. This is a violation of Article 18(3) of the ICCPR. Article 18(3), whereby preventing manifestation of religious beliefs is only permitted on grounds of public safety, order, health, morals or fundamental rights and freedoms of others (ICCPR, 1966). Discrimination in law extends to the Constitution itself.

2. Human Rights Violations: Discrimination and Exclusion

2.1 Marriage and Gender Segregation in Law

In terms of family law, the Supreme Court ruling in *Ghulam Mustafa v. Judge Family Court (2009 CLC 204)*, only grants marriage rights to intersex people with anatomical characteristics leaning towards either male or female. Intersex people with anatomical and/or biological characteristics which cannot be defined as such, simply cannot marry. Interestingly enough, the right to marry under Article 16(1) of the UDHR is also conferred specifically upon men and women (UDHR, 2016). This reflects the broader issue where binary gender

segregation in law excludes intersex individuals, denying them marriage rights and other civil liberties that remain largely restricted to “men” and “women” under Articles 16 and 23 of the ICCPR.

2.2 Discrimination in Health and Education

The 2018 Transgender Act provided some formal recognition, yet segregation and discrimination persist. In public spaces, intersex individuals face barriers, including medical certification requirements for identification, exclusion from gendered hospital wards, and public segregation (Lustgarten, 2023). This has tragic consequences, illustrated by the case of Alisha, an intersex person who was denied medical treatment due to gender discrimination. She was neither placed in the female ward, nor the male one, moving around the hospital until her demise. (Human Rights Watch, 2023). Lack of healthcare access and educational exclusion results in a vicious cycle of poverty and vulnerability for intersex individuals. Furthermore, with a majority of schools being segregated, intersex individuals are automatically excluded.

2.3 Economic Marginalisation and Inheritance Rights

Inheritance laws in Pakistan are largely based on Islamic principles, whereby men and women get different percentages of shares in inheritance. With the male portion being greater, many intersex individuals have chosen to identify as men in their official documents, even though this may not be reflective of their gender identity (Nisar, 2018). This essentially defeats the whole purpose of creating a third gender category, and reflects the ineffectiveness of doing so. Additionally, statutory

protections do not cover the intersex status, leaving individuals without legal guidance on property rights.

The lack of legislative clarity has contributed to economic marginalization, pushing many intersex individuals into informal, often exploitative employment, such as dancing or sex work (Manzoor, Aftab, & Yaqoob, 2019). This earns them meagre wages, reinforces harmful stereotypes and perpetuates the cycle of discrimination that already exists.

3. Social and Cultural Barriers: Harmful Practices and Stigmatization

3.1 Gender-Based Violence and Harmful Practices

Acts of violence against intersex individuals, including forced or medically unnecessary surgeries, are pervasive. These interventions often lack informed consent and are irreversible, violating both local laws and CRC standards, which require protection from such practices (Convention on the Rights of the Child, 1989). While this is not a common practice in Pakistan, where intersex babies are abandoned and where medical advancements might pose an issue, this is a possibility. The likelihood of this increases as tolerance increases. Where parents might choose to raise an intersex baby instead of abandoning it, due to gradual change in social attitudes, society may not have evolved enough for the child to be accepted as is. In such a situation, such surgeries have a strong likelihood of being favoured due to long-standing stigmatisation of gender-nonconformity.

In addition, intersex children frequently face abandonment or exploitation. Unregulated

“adoptions” by *Gurus* subject them to financial exploitation and abuse, as the guru culture controls their finances and social mobility under exploitative conditions (Boone, 2017).

3.2 Discrimination and Social Exclusion

Intersex individuals in Pakistan are subjected to derogatory labels like "Hijra" and "Khusra", often being the subject of mockery. This cultural intolerance has fueled discrimination in public spaces, education, and employment, where less than 15% of the intersex community has received basic education (Rana, 2023). These social attitudes reinforce barriers that prevent intersex individuals from accessing essential services, participating in social and religious practices, or enjoying public life, thus violating Article 25 of the ICCPR and Pakistan's Constitutional commitments to equality (ICCPR, 1966; OHCHR, n.d.).

Equally, the wider society's unwillingness to incorporate, integrate and accept intersex individuals. They may only exist in the margins, in a parallel subculture, interacting with wider society minimally.

3.3 Stigmatisation in Religion and Social Services

Religious exclusion is prominent, with intersex individuals barred from mosques or denied religious funeral rites, pushing them to create separate places of worship and burial grounds. This reflects a systemic failure to integrate intersex individuals into the broader community and provides no social protections against religious exclusion (Boone, 2017).

The shame associated with gender nonconformity is what leads to abandonment of intersex babies and lack of due paperwork upon birth. These individuals struggle to find a place in their families, places of worship, hospitals, and every public space there exists within society.

4. Shortcomings of Legal Protections and Challenges

4.1 Barriers to Justice and Law Enforcement Challenges

Legal obstacles prevent intersex individuals from seeking justice. Reports indicate that up to 68% avoid reporting crimes due to fear of discrimination and police bias, compounded by a lack of accessible complaint mechanisms (Gustavo & Gustavo, 2024).

Additionally, intersex individuals face discrimination within law enforcement, where they are not only marginalised but also face targeted violence by organised crime. Gang violence specifically exploits vulnerable individuals within the intersex community, with high incidences of sexual and physical abuse (Gustavo & Gustavo, 2024).

5. Comparative Analysis with International Human Rights Standards

5.1 Defining ‘Intersex’

As discussed above, the definition of ‘intersex’ itself within the Transgender Act 2018 is highly flawed. It is worth noting that the UN Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights defines ‘intersex individuals’ as people “born with sex characteristics (including genitals, gonads and chromosome patterns) that do not fit typical binary notions of male or female bodies.” This is a wider,

yet more precise definition as opposed to local legislation.

5.2 Lack of Compliance with the Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989)

As a party to the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) (1989), Pakistan is obligated to protect all children, including intersex children, from discrimination as per Article 2. Article 19 mandates protection from all forms of violence, neglect, and exploitation. However, these obligations remain unmet, as intersex babies are often abandoned or abused by their families. Abandoned intersex children are sometimes adopted into the Khawaja Sira community, where they receive shelter and food from *Gurus* in exchange for control over their finances and life decisions. These adoptions are unregulated and undocumented, leading to an exploitative system. Julie Khan, a prominent activist, refers to the culture as a ‘guru mafia.’

Additionally, Article 20 of the CRC states that a child deprived of a family environment is entitled to special protection and alternative care, which must be regulated under national laws. Article 21 emphasises that the best interests of the child must be the paramount consideration in any adoption, requiring authorization by competent authorities and informed consent from all parties involved. The failure to regulate these informal adoptions underlines Pakistan's non-compliance with its international law obligations under the CRC.

6. Recommendations

6.1 Policy and Legal Reforms

To bring about reforms the first step is to amend the Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act to include a precise definition of “intersex”,

aligning with OHCHR's standards to avoid ambiguity and improve accessibility to rights. Furthermore, laws and policies regulating adoptions of intersex babies, and protecting them upon abandonment, must be executed.

6.2 Health and Education Access

Crucial improvement is sought in the form of healthcare inclusion policies. Such policies should be implemented, requiring all public and private hospitals to provide unbiased treatment to intersex individuals, with sensitivity and inclusivity training programs for healthcare providers. Any medical care that may be required by an intersex individual should be readily available.

There is also a need for promotion of anti-discrimination campaigns and support education programs to improve public understanding of intersex rights, aiming to reduce stigma and increase intersex access to education and employment. A quota system in state schools, colleges and universities coupled with awareness campaigns among students is the need of the hour. Education can empower intersex individuals to not fall victim to the cycle of exploitative employment. It is also the first step to social integration, creating acceptance and tolerance among young students.

6.3 Data Collection and Monitoring

Data collection protocols must also be developed in order to collect comprehensive data on the intersex community, documenting cases of violence, discrimination, and human rights violations to inform policies and ensure accountability. Doing so is likely to help formulate

and implement targeted and effective policies and laws.

6.4 Strengthen Law Enforcement and Judicial Support

A major cause for ineffectiveness in the protection provided by law is lack of enforcement. The state must create accessible reporting channels for intersex individuals to report crimes without fear of discrimination and ensure protection against retaliation, such as creating a hotline specifically for this. More importantly, where hate crimes against intersex people occur, as far as possible, efforts must be made in order to locate the perpetrator so that legal recourse may be pursued. It is equally important to train law enforcement agencies to handle cases involving intersex individuals respectfully, addressing biases they may have, and encouraging the protection of intersex rights.

6.5 Legislative Reform

The repeals of section 2(f) and 3 of the Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act 2018 has left the *Khwaja Sira* community without the meagre protections they already had.

Keeping in mind the cultural and religious backdrop of Pakistan, the legislature must, with utmost transparency to the public, draft amendments to the Act. These should include precise definitions, and should be made following consultation with experts of law, medicine and of Islamic jurisprudence. More importantly, criticism and feedback from the *Khwaja Sira* community must be taken into consideration before enacting legislation. This can ensure clarity within future legislation; a much needed element to prevent further controversies and consequently repeals.

Legal recognition must be re-established as soon as possible. Furthermore, fundamental change in the curriculum should be brought about to integrate the Khwaja Sira community as normal and natural human beings. Teaching about the Khwaja Sira community at an early level in schools will also greatly help in creating further awareness and acceptance.

Conclusion

Pakistan's legal system must evolve to meet international human rights standards in addressing the needs of intersex individuals. While the Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act of 2018 was a significant step, it lacks clarity and fails to fully protect the rights of intersex individuals. Furthermore, the legal system has since retraced its steps and repealed some of the most essential provisions. Comprehensive reforms, including precise legal definitions, anti-discrimination measures, healthcare access, and data collection, are essential to ensure that Pakistan upholds its Constitutional and international commitments to human rights. Collaborative efforts with intersex advocacy groups, alongside effective policy and educational initiatives, are crucial in dismantling entrenched biases and fostering a more inclusive and just society for intersex individuals.

References

- Amnesty International. (2023). Pakistan: Government must reject proposed repeals of the Transgender Act.
- Boone, J. (2017, November 28). Pakistan transgender leader calls for end to culture of "gurus." *The Guardian*.
- Convention on the Rights of the Child, 1989.
- Gustavo, A., & Gustavo, A. (2024, February 13). Joint submission to the Universal Periodic Review on the Situation of LGBTI People in the Islamic Republic of Pakistan. GATE.
- Ghalib Naseer et al., (2024). Judicial activism: Authority or autocracy? Unravelling the role of judiciary in Pakistan. *The Institute of Legal Studies*.
- Human Rights Watch. (2023). When being counted can lead to being protected: Pakistan's transgender and intersex activists.
- ICCPR (1966). International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights.
- Manzoor, J., Aftab, S., & Yaqoob, M. (2019). Ambiguous genitalia: An overview of 7 years' experience at the Children's Hospital & Institute of Child Health, Lahore, Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences*.
- Nisar, M. (2021). Third Gender Recognition and the Khawaja Sira Community in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Gender Studies*.
- OHCHR. (n.d.). Discrimination and violence against intersex persons.